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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
GOVERNANCE IN THE UKRAINIAN EXPERIENCE**

**15-he Evolution of Legal Frameworks in
Lithuanian State Formation: Historical
Perspectives -and The Impact of European
Integration. By Lesia Kotsur and others.
p. 325.**

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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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(15)

**THE EVOLUTION OF LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN
LITHUANIAN STATE FORMATION:
HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVES
AND THE IMPACT OF EUROPEAN INTEGRATION**

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LESIA KOTSUR

PhD in History, Senior Lecturer, Associate Professor of Department of Political Sciences, Hryhorii Skovoroda University in Pereiaslav, Ukraine

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8996-1606>

dombrovska_ne@ukr.net

VITALII KOTSUR

PhD in Political Sciences, Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor of the Department of Public Administration, Rector of Hryhorii Skovoroda University in Pereiaslav, Pereiaslav, Ukraine.

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6647-7678>

kotsurv@ukr.net

ABSTRACT

Active European integration processes, which gained a new impetus in 2004, have demonstrated a new intensification of the geopolitical vector of the European community's enlargement. The study of different aspects of the European Union (EU) enlargement process is of particular importance, given the need to conceptualise future development strategies of the potential EU member states. It aims to analyse the dynamics of the legal framework of the state-building process in Lithuania from 1990 to 2022. The study conducts a comparative analysis of historical aspects of the experience in the context of the period before and after the European integration processes. The research identifies a significant regulatory and systemic gap between these periods in terms of the development of the legislative field. Significant concepts in the context of the vectoriality of integration processes and the formation of long-term economic policy in the region are identified. The specifics of Lithuania's integration into the European environment are analysed. The main stages of the studied process are allocated. The basic mechanisms and principles of implementing

an effective European integration policy are revealed. The problems accompanying the process of adaptation of the legal framework to the requirements of the European Union in the context of state-building processes are studied. It is proved that the historical experience of the Republic of Lithuania in terms of the active influence of foreign policy processes on the strategy and practice of integration into the EU is positioned as indicative of Ukraine since both countries have similar initial conditions and are characterised by historical proximity. The study identifies the states that had the most significant impact on the processes of democratisation and state-building in Lithuania. It is proved that Lithuania's integration into the European community has a specific individuality due to the institutional support and specificity of constitutional processes, which is determinative in settling issues between the Lithuanian government and EU institutions.

Keywords: European integration processes, regulatory and legal support, state-building, institutions, the Republic of Lithuania.

1- INTRODUCTION

Legal and regulatory support is the basis and one of the necessary prerequisites for an effective state-building process. When analysing the processes of statehood formation in the countries that emerged from the Soviet formation in the early 1990s, it is worth highlighting Lithuania's position. In the context of retrospective analysis, the Republic of Lithuania is currently positioned as the most successful of the post-Soviet states. Obviously, the regulatory framework played a significant role in the processes of establishing democracy and European-oriented statehood.

The Baltic states' pro-Western orientation prompted the governments of the newly formed countries after the collapse of the USSR to quickly identify strategic development priorities. The Republic of Lithuania, in this case, took the European concept of socio-economic development as a basis. Thus, Lithuania demonstrated its readiness to integrate into the EU and positioned such intentions as the chosen path of strengthening sovereignty and national independence.

Lithuania's European integration priority was expressed long before its practical implementation. An example is the "Return to the West" project implemented by anti-Russian leadership groups. In the context of Ukraine, the relevance of studying the legal framework for forming Lithuania's statehood is due to several factors. In particular, both countries have common initial conditions after the collapse of the Soviet Union, including socio-economic ones, as well as well-established European integration aspirations in domestic and foreign policy. In this regard, studying the historical experience of statehood and democracy in Lithuania has significant practical potential for Ukraine, including determining the influence of neighbouring countries on the progress of the processes under study.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Several scholars have reflected on the issues under study in publications and scientific works. In particular, various aspects of this issue are covered by Astrauskas¹, Trabucco², Virgilijus³, Petryshyn⁴, Mindaugas⁵, Vytautas⁶ and Žalimas^{7, 8}. The authors study the dynamics of regulatory and legal support against the background of Lithuania's active integration into the European environment. Scholars position Lithuania as a pioneer of democratic transformation in the region.

In the Ukrainian scientific field, most researchers are convinced that the experience of the Republic of Lithuania in terms of the impact of the foreign policy situation on the processes of state-building and European integration is positioned as indicative of Ukraine. For example, Kotsur⁹ is convinced that national movements in Ukraine have historically suffered more significant devastating losses, which has weakened the phenomenon of statehood compared to Lithuanian ones. The researcher is confident that this has led to the long-term ineffectiveness of reforms in this area.

According to Mahomedov¹⁰, the socio-political dynamics in Lithuania and Ukraine, despite the presence of decisive destructive factors of influence, were positioned as a driving force for transforming the format of foreign policy activity. The author believes that social aspects, in cooperation with global institutions, have helped form a stable trend of developing European integration of post-Soviet countries.

¹ Astrauskas, A. (2015). Lietuvos vietos savivaldos sistemos raida nuo 1990 metų iki šių dienų. *Public policy and administration*, 4, 604-616.

² Trabucco, F. R. (2017). *Local Self-Government Development in Lithuania*. The Netherlands: Kluwer Law International BV. 268 p.

³ Virgilijus, Č. (2007). *Su Sąjūdžiu už Lietuvą: nuo 1988 06 03 iki 1990 03 11*. Vilnius: Tvermė.

⁴ Petryshyn, O. O. (2013). The system of local self-government in Lithuania: prospects for using the experience in the context of municipal reform in Ukraine. *Bulletin of the National Academy of Legal Sciences of Ukraine*, 3.

⁵ Mindaugas, M. (2005). *Lietuvos valstybės konstitucijų istorija (XX a. pirmoji pusė)*. Vilnius: Justitia.

⁶ Vytautas, S. (2012). Kovo 11-oji: Nepriklausomybės atkūrimo teisinė konstrukcija. *Jurisprudencija*, 3, 55-71.

⁷ Žalimas, D. (2010a). *Sąjūdis ir Lietuvos Respublikos Nepriklausomybės atkūrimas, Kelias į Nepriklausomybę: Lietuvos Sąjūdis 1988-1991, sudarė Bronislovas Genzelis ir Angonita Rupšytė*. Kaunas: Šviesa. <https://www.lituanistika.lt/content/91612>

⁸ Žalimas, D. (2010b). *Sąjūdžio kelias į kovo 11-oją: nuo "tarybinio" valstybingumo iki Lietuvos valstybės tęstinumo koncepcijos*. <https://repository.mruni.eu/bitstream/handle/007/17995/9789955192480-77-107.pdf?sequence=1>

⁹ Kotsur, V. V. (2019). *National minorities of Ukraine in the context of socio-political transformations of the 90s of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century. Monograph*. Pereiaslav-Khmelnyskyi.

¹⁰ Mahomedov, A. V. (2022). *Ukraine and NATO in the context of socio-political transformations of the 90s of the twentieth and early twenty-first centuries. Monograph*. Pereiaslav-Khmelnyskyi: Hryhorii Skovoroda University of Pereiaslav.

In turn, Masyk¹¹ argues that Lithuania is positioned as an active political player in the region despite the accompanying difficulties. The author describes Lithuania as a state with defined strategic values, tasks, and a development concept that has managed to implement the necessary structural reforms in difficult economic conditions. This has enabled it to find its own place in the architecture of the European community.

It is worth noting that the works of these scholars have specific theoretical and methodological potential; however, comparing the historical experience of forming the legal framework of state building in Lithuania with the concept of the European integration process has been studied fragmentarily. This underlines the relevance of the topic of this study.

The study aims to analyse the dynamics of the legal framework of the state-building process in Lithuania from 1990 to 2022.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study used general and special scientific methods. In particular, systematic analysis, synthesis, comparison, and scientific abstraction were used, as well as the functional method, sociological and historical methods, and comparative legal methods.

The research process involved two main stages: collecting informative data and analytical processing. In the first stage, primary sources of information were used. The research materials included industry-specific scientific papers, publications, and materials from scientific and practical conferences in the industry. The sample size of the information sources was justified in the context of practical realities necessary for the successful implementation of the study.

With the help of scientific abstraction and system analysis, the essence of the phenomenon of state-building in Lithuania was determined, and the main functionality, methods and tools of this process were identified. The systemic analysis allowed to establish the essence of definitions and conceptual categories, while the synthesis allowed a combination of the selected aspects in a meaningful way from the identical and essential to the diversity, integrating general and individual aspects into a single concept, thus characterising the peculiarities of the influence of foreign policy factors on the processes of Lithuania's formation as a state.

The study uses the abstraction of potential practical feasibility, which is considered a mental distraction from the standard properties of state-building in the regulatory and legal aspects, with simultaneous identification of the desired significant properties.

The functional method was used to determine the goals of the processes under study, while the sociological method was used to summarise empirical information. The historical method was used to study the evolution of the phenomenon under study. The comparative legal method made it possible to identify the specifics of the impact of foreign policy factors on the processes of state-building, European integration and the establishment of democracy in Lithuania in 1990-2022 in the evolutionary context.

¹¹ Masyk, Yu. R. (2020). Stages of the Baltic states' European integration process: experience for Ukraine. *Bulletin of NTUU "KPI" Political science. Sociology. Law*, 2(46). [https://doi.org/10.20535/2308-5053.2020.2\(46\).226606](https://doi.org/10.20535/2308-5053.2020.2(46).226606)

4. RESULTS

A comparative analysis of the impact of foreign policy factors on the processes of state-building and democracy in Lithuania requires an extended study of the context of the initial conditions under which the country regained its independence.

In general, the process of Lithuania's state-building and the formation of its European integration strategy can be differentiated into the following stages:

1) 1990-1997 – integration of the decentralised system and its gradual simplification, administrative and territorial reform, redistribution of powers and functions of institutions;

2) 1997-2005 – development of the discourse on regional policy development and administrative supervision over the development of decentralisation and democratic processes;

3) 2005-2010 – preparations for the implementation of several legislative decisions in the context of European integration, statehood and democracy;

4) from 2010 to the present, there has been an active European integration policy, elimination of district administrations, creation of regional development councils, and economically oriented social development.

The reform movements of the late 1980s are considered the beginning of the intensification of establishing Lithuania's statehood. Their main idea was to restore national law, integrate democratic principles, and implement European norms. The democratic movement *Sąjūdis* became the organisational centre of social transformations¹².

At that time, prognostic legal documents were developed and adopted after the restoration of state independence began. This is confirmed by the analysis of the work of the newly elected Sejm on February 24, 1990, whose majority was made up of the democratic forces of *Sąjūdis*. The Sejm began its work on March 10, 1990, after the second round of parliamentary elections.

Lithuania's close cultural and religious ties with Western European countries, as well as the Indo-European origin of the Lithuanian language, were additional catalysts for the development of European integration sentiments.

After choosing the course of rapprochement with the EU in 1991, the Republic of Lithuania joined the North Atlantic Cooperation Council. Since then, Lithuania has been positioned as a beneficiary of support programmes from the European community. Subsequently, the Baltic Assembly, a body of inter-parliamentary cooperation with a European integration focus, was established on Lithuania's initiative. In 1995, Lithuania signed the European Association Agreement.

Despite Lithuania's active foreign policy efforts, the need for socio-economic reforms played a significant role, as the post-Soviet influence was reflected in the predominance of the public sector in the economy and the inconsistency of national legislation with European standards. This required significant domestic political efforts

¹² Peters, I. (2018). 30 years of *Sąjūdis*. From the movement for perestroika to Lithuanian independence. *Radio Liberty*. <https://www.svoboda.org/a/29268457.html>

to reform social and political processes. The radical nature of the reforms was a key prerequisite for Lithuania's successful accession to the EU in 2004.

When the Seimas began functioning in 1990, the first draft laws were considered: "On the Name and Emblem of the State", "On the Restoration of the Constitution of Lithuania of May 12 1938", "On the Extension of Powers of Certain State Bodies of the Republic of Lithuania" and "On the Temporary Fundamental Law of the Republic of Lithuania"^{13, 14}.

Active legislative activity continued in the following months, when the Lithuanian parliament considered the invalidation of the Law on the Universal Military Service of the USSR on the territory of the Republic of Lithuania¹⁵, changes in the status of state-owned enterprises¹⁶, marking the state border¹⁷.

Moscow's reaction was not sharp due to Russia's internal problems and the expectation of support from Lithuanian deputies¹⁸. At the same time, immediately after the declaration of independence, Russia intensified the activities of communists in Lithuania in order to destabilise the political situation. They provoked separatist sentiments, for example, by inciting the Lithuanian military to resist, exerting propaganda pressure through the channels of central Soviet television, and attempting to create parallel state structures^{19, 20, 21, 22}.

In response, on March 26 1990, the Sejm adopted a resolution to normalise the country's situation²³. The government was formed, making it ready to implement new economic reforms²⁴.

¹³ Transcript (May 31 1990). Evening session, document 75. <http://surl.li/aahez>

¹⁴ Lietuvos Nepriklausomybės atkūrimas 1990 kovo 11 d. Lietuvos Respublikos Seimo kanceliarija, biudžetinė įstaiga. https://www.lrs.lt/sip/portal.show?p_r=37675&p_k=1

¹⁵ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 5]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 12 d. <http://surl.li/dwelip>

¹⁶ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 4]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 12 d. <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.251085>

¹⁷ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 13]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 20 d. <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.251064>

¹⁸ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 10]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 17 d. <http://surl.li/iiodpii>

¹⁹ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 6]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990. kovo 13 d. <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.251087>

²⁰ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 8]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 14 d. <http://surl.li/blksxl>

²¹ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 9]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 14 d. <http://surl.li/rkfkhm>

²² Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 11]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 17 d. <http://surl.li/iqocch>

²³ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 23]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. kovo 26 d. <http://surl.li/ozbjja>

Given the economic blockade provoked by the Kremlin, the Lithuanian parliament focused on the relevant legislation on anti-blockade measures²⁵. The same blockade did not prevent the Lithuanian parliament from starting to prepare documents for agrarian reform²⁶.

In early 1991, the situation between Lithuania and the USSR deteriorated, prompting the Seimas to adopt a resolution on measures for the defence of the Republic of Lithuania²⁷. After the USSR used military force, which resulted in the deaths of more than 14 people²⁸, the Lithuanian parliament's resolve did not weaken, which was reflected in the promptly adopted Law on Emigration of the Government of the Republic of Lithuania (January 13 1991).

Despite the situation's complications, the Lithuanian parliament and society withstood the pressure. To this end, a plebiscite was organised on February 9, 1991, to determine the level of approval of the draft Constitution of the Republic of Lithuania. 90.47 percent of the plebiscite was held in favour, which contributed to the adoption of the Constitutional Law on the State of Lithuania²⁹.

In the following years, the constitutional process, institutional development and the restoration of control over state security were actively developed. In particular, a decision was made to hold a referendum on the unconditional and immediate withdrawal of former Soviet troops from the territory of the Republic of Lithuania³⁰. Also, a new law on elections to the Seimas was adopted, the most important innovation of which was the establishment of a mixed electoral system³¹.

The culmination of state-building activities at that time was the new Constitution of the Republic of Lithuania (October 25 1992). This is the only Constitution of

²⁴ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 36]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. balandžio 5 d. <http://surl.li/dksocs>

²⁵ Stenograma [Dokumento tekstas, No. 48]. Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba. 1990 m. balandžio 24 d. <http://surl.li/mmsqht>

²⁶ Transcript (May 31, 1990). *Id.*

²⁷ Transcript (January 12, 1991) Evening session, no. 91. <http://surl.li/bqmaon>

²⁸ Transcript (January 14, 1991). Morning session, no. 93. Information from the head of the funeral commission Z. Vaishvili. <http://surl.li/qxdhpt>

²⁹ Kruopienė, V. (Red.). (2017). *Lietuvos konstitucinė teisė: Vadovėlis (2-oji laida)*. VĮ Registru centras. <http://surl.li/vprvni>

³⁰ Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba – Atkuriamasis Seimas. (1992 m. birželio 16 d.). *Šimtas keturiasdešimt trečiasis posėdis: Stenograma.* <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.251505>

³¹ Lietuvos Respublikos Aukščiausioji Taryba – Atkuriamasis Seimas. (1992 m. liepos 9 d.). *Šimtas šešiasdešimt pirmasis posėdis: Stenograma.* <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.251666>

Lithuania adopted by referendum, which was supported by almost 81% of Lithuanian citizens (1.5 million voters)³².

After the adoption of the Constitution, the traditional state parliament, the Seimas, replaced the Restoration Seimas, significantly affecting the functioning of the entire legislature³³. Also, the presidency was restored in 1993, making Lithuania a semi-presidential republic³⁴.

In 1995, tough legislative initiatives were launched to harmonise domestic acts with EU regulations and strengthen the state's national structure.

First of all, we are talking about:

- The Law on the State Language of the Republic of Lithuania (January 31 1995), which established the use of the state language (Lithuanian) in public life of Lithuania, protected and controlled the state language^{35, 36};
- the Resolution "On the Reorganisation of the Energy System"³⁷;
- Laws regulating the activities of NGOs and political parties and others³⁸.

Most of the bills aimed to adapt to the European legal system, allowing Lithuania to sign the Association Agreement with the EU on June 12 1995³⁹. After this, the work of the Lithuanian parliament became even more active. Between 1996 and 2000, 3000 draft laws were registered in the Seimas, and 2223 were approved.

On November 6 1997, the Seimas of the Republic of Lithuania adopted the resolution "On Government Priorities for Lithuania's Integration into the European Union." This resolution formed the basis of the National Acquis Implementation

³² Lietuvos Respublikos Seimo kanceliarija. (2017). *Kelias į Lietuvos Respublikos Konstituciją: Lietuvos Respublikos Konstitucijai – 30*. In *Parodos parlamentarizmo istorijos temomis*. Lietuvos Respublikos Seimo kanceliarija. https://www.lrs.lt/sip/portal.show?p_r=37137&p_k=1

³³ Blažytė-Baužienė, D. (2004). Lietuvos Parlamentarai 1990-2004 metais. *Parlamento studijos*, 2. https://journals.lnb.lt/ps-archyvas/Nr3/Istorija_Blazyte.htm

³⁴ Bitautas, A. (2018). Kaip ten iš tikrųjų buvo valdant A. Brazauskui. *Parlamento studijos*, 25, 2015-222. <https://journals.lnb.lt/ps-archyvas/Nr25/files/215-223.pdf>

³⁵ Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas. (1995 m. sausio 31 d.). *Šešiasdešimt aštuntasis posėdis: Stenograma*. <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.239051>

³⁶ Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas. (1995 m. sausio 31 d.). *Lietuvos Respublikos valstybinės kalbos įstatymas* (Nr. I-779). <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.15211?jfwid=32wf6lrn>

³⁷ Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas. (1995 m. sausio 31 d.). *Šešiasdešimt devintasis posėdis: Stenograma*.

³⁸ Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas. (1995 m. vasario 2 d.). *Septyniadesimtas posėdis: Stenograma*. <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAK/TAIS.239053>

³⁹ Lietuvos Respublikos Seimo kanceliarija. (2022, lapkričio 23). *Lietuvos ir ES sąveikos istorija*. https://www.lrs.lt/sip/portal.show?p_r=39134&p_k=1

Programme (NAPP), approved by the Seimas on March 17 1998⁴⁰. This seriously affected Lithuania, which launched a series of reforms⁴¹.

Lithuania was admitted to the EU on May 1, 2004, when it fulfilled the roadmap. At the initial stage, Lithuania adopted the Constitutional Act on the Membership of the Republic of Lithuania in the European Union⁴². The ESTEP (European Social, Legal and Economic Projects) report on the implementation of EU norms in Lithuania, published on January 10, 2012, documented the extent of Lithuania's achievements during this period.

The report classifies the legal acts regulating the implementation of EU norms in Lithuania into three stages:

- 1) before joining the EU, which contributed to the completion of the roadmap;
- 2) 2004-2009 - establishing coordination of the system of transposition and implementation of EU legislation with the creation of a separate information system for document flow between Lithuania and the EU;
- 3) since 2009, EU norms have been integrated into the Republic of Lithuania's system of state authorities.

When assessing the state-building activities of the Lithuanian parliament before and after EU integration, it is worth noting that the common feature is that the decisions taken by the parliament concerned the institutionalisation of democracy, redistribution of governmental powers, introduction of new political and cultural values, and standards of socio-cultural behaviour⁴³.

European integration has become the primary catalyst for social and political reforms and economic growth. Following this path, Lithuania has transformed its legal framework in line with the Copenhagen criteria, bringing the country closer to the level of a consolidated democracy. One of the most important conditions for EU accession is the transfer of control over the country's judiciary⁴⁴. This project allowed us to identify existing problems in Lithuania's EU law development system and propose modern optimisation solutions based on the best European practices.

Today, Lithuania positions itself as an active shaper of the EU's Eastern policy. The country's main initiative regarding Ukraine is the official recognition of Ukraine as a candidate for EU membership during Lithuania's second presidency of the Council of

⁴⁰ Lietuvos Respublikos Seimas. (1998 m. kovo 17 d.). *Dėl Nacionalinės ACQUIS priėmimo programos įgyvendinimo: Rezoliucija*. <http://surl.li/dwhyxa>

⁴¹ Astrauskas, A. (2015). *Id.*

⁴² Trainauskienė, S. (2009). *Narystės Europos Sąjungoje įtaka parlamento ir vyriausybės santykiams. Parlamento studijos, 8*. https://journals.lnb.lt/ps-archyvas/Nr8/8_sociologija_1.htm

⁴³ Lukošaitis, A. (2020). *Teisėkūra Lietuvoje: instituciniai ir kultūriniai problemų suvokimo fragmentai. Parlamento studijos, 28, 24-46*. <https://journals.lnb.lt/ps-archyvas/Nr28/files/24-46.pdf>

⁴⁴ *Europos socialiniai, teisiniai ir ekonominiai projektai (ESTEP)*. (2012, sausio 10 d.). *Europos Sąjungos teisės plėtros ir įgyvendinimo sistemos Lietuvos Respublikoje veiksmingumo stiprinimas: Galutinė tyrimo ataskaita* (p. 198). <http://surl.li/psbwrt>

the European Union, which will take place in 2027. Vilnius is trying to play the role of the main European expert on reforms in Ukraine and a committed advocate in the EU.

The constitutionally enshrined European course should be supported by the adoption of several legal acts in synergy with the implementation of practical measures to promote the basic values of a democratic society.

5-DISCUSSION

Several researchers are convinced that the experience of the Republic of Lithuania in studying the impact of the foreign policy situation on the processes of integration into the European community is indicative of Ukraine due to the presence of common initial characteristics, historical proximity of the states, and the relatively short experience of modern independent statehood of Ukraine and Lithuania, despite their significant historical achievements.

According to scholars Petryshyn⁴⁵ and Trabucco⁴⁶, socio-political transformations have become a driving force in Lithuania. They prompted a radical transformation of the relations strategy in the Republic's foreign policy. Also, according to the authors, against the background of socio-political transformations, the process of cooperation with global institutions aimed at European integration within the framework of the sustainable development strategy has become more relevant.

According to Virgilijus⁴⁷ and Astrauskas⁴⁸, the results of the analysis of the historical preconditions for democratic state-building and the establishment of democracy in Lithuania and in the context of different countries make the potential of the historical conceptualisation of European integration processes especially important.

According to Vytautas⁴⁹ and Mindaugas⁵⁰, Lithuania positions itself as a vivid example of an active participant in European regional development. By timely defining strategic goals, it has managed to implement the necessary structural reforms in the context of European integration.

Based on the practical experience of Lithuania, Žalimas^{51, 52, 53} believes that the promising vector of development of developing countries seeking European integration

⁴⁵ Petryshyn, O. O. (2013). *Id.*

⁴⁶ Trabucco, F. R. (2017). *Id.*

⁴⁷ Virgilijus, Č. (2007). *Id.*

⁴⁸ Astrauskas, A. (2015). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Vytautas, S. (2012). *Id.*

⁵⁰ Mindaugas, M. (2005). *Id.*

⁵¹ Žalimas, D. (2008). *Lietuvos Respublikos nepriklausomybės atkūrimo 1990 metais teisiniai pagrindai*. Vilnius: Žaltvykslė

⁵² Žalimas, D. (2010a). *Id.*

should include optimisation of public management models and regulatory and legal upgrade of integration processes into the European environment.

CONCLUSION

In the context of studying the process's multipolar aspects, active European integration processes require the conceptualisation of future development strategies of the potential EU member states. An analysis of the dynamics of the legal framework for the state-building process in Lithuania from 1990 to 2022 has shown a significant regulatory and systemic gap in terms of the development of the legislative field between these periods.

After choosing the course of rapprochement with the EU in 1991, the Republic of Lithuania joined the North Atlantic Cooperation Council. Since then, Lithuania has been positioned as a beneficiary of support programmes from the European community. When assessing the state-building activities of the Lithuanian parliament before and after EU integration, it is worth noting that the common feature is that the decisions taken by the parliament concerned the institutionalisation of democracy, redistribution of governmental powers, introduction of new political and cultural values, and standards of socio-cultural behaviour.

The specificity of Lithuania's integration into the European environment lies in the stages of the studied process. Lithuania's integration into the European community has a specific individuality due to the institutional support and specificity of constitutional processes, which is determinative in settling issues between the Lithuanian government and the EU institutions. The historical experience of the Republic of Lithuania in actively influencing foreign policy processes on the strategy and practice of EU integration is indicative of Ukraine, as both countries have similar initial conditions and are characterised by historical proximity.

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⁵³ Žalimas, D. (2010b). *Id.*

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